

Benzimidazoles. Part I. Metal Ion Promoted Hydrolysis of 1-N-Morpholinomethyl Benzimidazole

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WE wish to report that in the presence of metal ions 1-N-morpholinomethyl benzimidazole¹ (I) is hydrolysed to benzimidazole which then forms a complex with the metal ion while 1-hydroxymethyl benzimidazole^{1,2} (II) undergoes facile hydrolysis to benzimidazole in hot aqueous solution alone:

Experimental

1-N-Morpholinomethyl benzimidazole was recovered unchanged after 2 hr digestion with water on a steam bath (yield, 80%; m.p. 109°; lit.¹, 110.5° to 111.5°; Found: N, 20.0; Calc.: 19.3%).

Reactions of metal ions with 1-N-morpholinomethyl benzimidazole: The ligand (0.0025 mole) was dissolved in water (50 ml.). To this was added an aqueous solution of cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate, nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate or zinc(II) chloride dihydrate (0.0012 mole) and the mixture digested on a steam bath for 2 hr. The precipitate was collected, washed with water and alcohol and dried in air. The reaction of copper(II) acetate monohydrate (0.0012 mole) and the ligand (0.0025 mole) was performed in rectified spirit (75 ml.).

1-Hydroxymethyl benzimidazole was obtained following two procedures^{1,2}. *Rapid crystallisation* from hot aqueous alcohol or hot water gave the same m.p. 143°. When the compound (1 g in 200 ml water) was digested on a steam bath for 3 hr, cooled and the resulting precipitate recrystallised from hot water, a product with m.p. 172° was obtained. (Found: N, 24.1; Calc. for benzimidazole 23.7%; m.p.³ 170°).

Although Mannich reaction products are usually susceptible to hydrolysis⁴, 1-N-morpholinomethyl benzimidazole can be safely recrystallised after digestion in hot water. 'Super acid' behaviour⁵ of metal ions such as cobalt(II), nickel(II), zinc(II) and copper(II) does promote the hydrolytic process decomposing 1-N-morpholinomethyl benzimidazole to simple benzimidazole which then forms bis(benzimidazolato) metal(II) complexes. Their identity has been established through elemental analyses and a comparison with authentic samples under the microscope (Table 1). The filtrate from the metal ion reaction products gives positive dinitrophenyl hydrazine test for formaldehyde (Found: m.p. 164°, formaldehyde D.N.P.⁶, m.p. 167°).

The metal ion tends to establish a coordinate link with the imidazole nitrogen which makes the methylene carbon much too positive (δ^+)—much above what accrues on it due to an electronegativity difference alone between the imidazole nitrogen and the methylene carbon. This enhanced δ^+ facilitates a nucleophilic attack by H₂O on the methylene carbon as depicted below, resulting in the rupture of the nitrogen-methylene carbon linkage.

Bachman and Heisay¹ prepared 1-hydroxymethyl benzimidazole by reacting benzimidazole and formaldehyde in methanol (reported m.p. 143°) while Hideg and Hankovszky² obtained the same compound from ethanol medium (reported m.p. 173°–174°). We have repeated both the procedures and obtained the same compound (m.p. 143°). Both the products showed similar fine needles under the microscope and reacted with morpholine to give 1-N-morpholinomethyl benzimidazole (Found: m.p. 110°).

1-Hydroxymethyl benzimidazole suffers hydrolysis to benzimidazole on digestion in hot water for a few hours, giving a positive D.N.P. test (Found: m.p.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION OF THE PRODUCTS OF REACTION OF 1-N-MORPHOLINOMETHYL BENZIMIDAZOLE WITH METAL IONS

Metal Ion	Reaction product	Colour	Analysis			
			Metal		Nitrogen	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Co(II)	[Co(benzimidazolato) ₂]	Brilliant violet	19.5	20.1	19.3	19.1
Cu(II)	[Cu(benzimidazolato) ₂]	Chocolate red	21.3	21.4	18.5	18.8
Ni(II)	[Ni(benzimidazolato) ₂]	Dirty ash violet	19.2	20.0	19.1	19.1
Zn(II)	[Zn(benzimidazolato) ₂]	White	21.7	21.9	18.7	18.7

165°). The pronounced electronegativity of oxygen is likely to make the methylene carbon much too positive (δ^+) compared to the methylene carbon atom of the 1-N-morpholinomethyl benzimidazole leading to a facile nucleophilic by water alone. 'Super acid' character of metal ions is no longer necessary to decompose this Mannich product.

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Irisolidone from *Iris kashmiriana* Baker

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IRISOLIDONE has previously been isolated by Prakash *et al.*¹, from petroleum-ether extract of *Iris nepalensis*.

During the exhaustive chemical investigation of *I. kashmiriana* Baker, the title compound was found to be one of the constituents of CHCl_3 extract of defatted rhizomes. Its identity was established from the following physico-chemical constants: m.p. 188.5° (lit., 195–96¹ and 191–92²), Rf. 0.4 (CHCl_3 : EtoAc,

2.5:0.2), $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$, uv: $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ at 268, 330 nm (shoulder) shifting to 278 and 276 nm upon the addition of AlCl_3 and NaOAc, respectively. IR shows bands at 3400, 1655, 1633, 1580, 1463, 1368, 1296, 1232, 1160, 1072, 830 and 815 cm^{-1} . NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.96s, 2-H; 7.56d (JAB = 9 Hz), 2',6'-H; 7.11d (JAB = 9 Hz), 3',5'-H; 6.61s, 8-H and 7-OH; 3.9s and 4.08s, two- OCH_3 protons. D_2O exchange reduces the signal at 6.61 to one proton signal. (signal due to 5-OH), which appears above δ 10 has not been recorded. MS: M^+ 314 and other major fragments at m/e 315, 299, 296, 271 and 69.

Acetate (Ac_2O -Pyridine): m.p. 213° (lit¹ 163°), ir: 1773, 1648, 1623, 1515, 1481, 1435, 1373, 1297, 1247, 1185, 1062, 1028, 904, 855 and 750 cm^{-1} , nmr (CDCl_3) δ : 7.82s, 2-H; 7.38d (JAB = 9 Hz), 2',6'-H; 6.93d (JAB = 9 Hz), 3',5'-H; 7.15s, 8-H (a typical downfield shift in 5-acetoxy flavonoids)²; 3.81s and 3.85s, two OCH_3 proton signals; 2.34s and 2.42s, two acetate proton signals. IR and nmr indicate that both the -OH groups are acetylated in the acetate.

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